

Application of the SlideforMap model for the hydrological risk assessment in sustainably managed forests

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General information about operational group BIOSEIFORTE

BIO.S.E.I.FOR.TE. (BIODiversity and Ecosystem Services In FOREST and TERRitory) is a project funded by the rural development plan Marche 2014/2020 - Call Sub-measure 16.1 Operation A “Support to the creation and operation of EIP Operational Groups”- Action 2 “Financing of Operational Groups”. The objective of BIOSEIFORTE was to identify and enhance the main ecosystem services in the Monte Nerone district (Pesaro-Urbino, Marche), located in the northern sector of the Umbria-Marches Apennines, with the active participation of local communities and frequent visitors. Ecosystem services, referring to the utilities that sustainable management of forest and land resources provides, consider the protection of biodiversity and from hydrogeological hazards and the conservation of traditional products such as wood, milk, and meat.

The Monte Nerone Forestry Consortium was the project leader, while the Forest Systems Area of the Department of Agricultural, Food, and Environmental Sciences of the Università Politecnica delle Marche (UNIVPM) was in charge of the scientific coordination of the project. Other partners included the Medit Silva Foundation, acting as editor, and Impresa Verde Marche SRL with Federforeste (Italian Federation of Forest Communities), which handled dissemination and support to local forest communities, respectively.

Statistical information

Landslides are endangering inhabited areas all around the world. In the period from 1994 to 2023, they represent 17 % of natural hazard fatalities.^[1] From 2010 to 2019, the annual cash monetary loss averaged approximately 25 billion USD. ^[2] A significant increase in damage caused by hydrologically related natural hazards, including shallow landslides, was noted by the Swiss Re Institute over the past five years.^[3]

In the Alpine parts of Switzerland, 74 people died because of a landslide event in the period from 1946 to 2015. ^[4]

In mountainous regions, rain-induced shallow landslides are among the most critical and dangerous types of mass movement.^[5] The standard definition of shallow landslide is: “Translational mass movement with maximum soil thickness of two meters.”

[1] Kjekstad O., Highland L. 2009. Economic and social impacts of landslides. V: Landslides – Disaster Risk Reduction, Sassa K., Canuti P. (ur.). Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg: 573–587. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-540-69970-5_30.

[2] Munich RE: Relevant hydrological events worldwide 1980–2018. Münchener Rückversicherungs- Gesellschaft, NatCatService. <https://www.munichre.com/en/solutions/for-industry-clients/natcatservice.html> (2. 7. 2020).

[3] Swiss Re Institute. 2019. Natural catastrophes and man-made disasters in 2018: “secondary” perils on the frontline. Sigma, 2019, 2: 1–36.

[4] Badoux A., Andres N., Techel F., Hegg C. 2016. Natural hazard fatalities in Switzerland from 1946 to 2015. Natural Hazards and Earth System Sciences, 16: 2747–2768. <https://doi.org/10.5194/nhess-16-2747-2016>.

[5] Varnes D.J. 1978. Slope movement types and processes. Special Report, 176: 11–33. <https://onlinepubs.trb.org/Onlinepubs/sr/sr176/176-002.pdf> (28. 2. 2025)

Summary

Rain-induced shallow landslides pose a natural hazard for the human environment – both natural and man-made. One of the expected consequences of climate change is the increased frequency and intensity of critical rainfall events, which are one of the main triggering processes of shallow landslides. That is the reason for identifying mitigation strategies is increasingly urgent. Developing reliable^[6] allows us to identify areas most susceptible to landslides and optimize the function of direct protect forests by planning the correct management. SlideforMAP is a probabilistic slope stability model, applicable at regional scale^[7], that considers the effect of root reinforcement in guaranteeing slope stability, providing a set of valuable products for land-use and forestry planning to mitigate instability.

Introduction

Shallow landslides pose a threat for human lives and infrastructure; therefore, slope stability models are important. They are valuable tools to examine mitigation practices against catastrophic effects caused by shallow landslides. One example of such a tool is the model SlideforMAP^[8].

SlideforMAP helps identify and plan more adequate silvicultural practices that can improve the protective effect of forests and reduce the risk of triggering shallow

landslides^[9].

Shallow landslides are characterized by scar thickness of less than two meters. Because they represent a danger to infrastructure, residential areas, and human lives, probabilistic slope stability models were developed. One of them is SlideforMap, which enables a regional assessment of the shallow landslides probability while considering various scenarios of forest cover, forest management, and rainfall intensity. Using a probabilistic approach, SlideforMAP generates hypothetical landslides and, for each, verifies the stability through the balance calculation considering hydro-mechanical parameters. The model requires input parameters data about morphology, soil characteristics, forest structure and composition, and the rainfall event information to be simulated. Based on these data, it calculates the landslide probability. Calibration of SlideforMAP was performed in three different areas in Switzerland. They are all located in mountainous areas with reliable landslide inventory. The study shows that the observed occurrence of shallow landslides at the catchment scale can be reproduced by the approach, used in SlideforMAP.^[10]

The use of slope stability models has proven to be necessary in various circumstances, for example development of hazard maps of shallow landslides susceptibility and quantification of frequency of occurrence of such events.

[6] Murgia I., Giadrossich F., Mao Z., Cohen D., Capra G.F., Schwarz M. 2022. Modeling shallow landslides and root reinforcement: A review. *Ecological Engineering*, 2022, 181: 106671. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoleng.2022.106671>.

[7] Murgia I. 2022. The role of forests in soil protection: root reinforcement and slope stability evaluation at different analysis scales. PhD Thesis. University of Sassari, Department of Architecture, Design and Urban Planning: IX. <https://hdl.handle.net/20.500.14242/87876> (28. 2.2025).

[8] Murgia I., Giadrossich F., Mao Z., Cohen D., Capra G.F., Schwarz M. 2022. Modeling shallow landslides and root reinforcement: A review. *Ecological Engineering*, 2022, 181: 106671. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoleng.2022.106671>.

[9] Murgia I., Giadrossich F., Mao Z., Cohen D., Capra G.F., Schwarz M. 2022. Modeling shallow landslides and root reinforcement: A review. *Ecological Engineering*, 2022, 181: 106671. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoleng.2022.106671>.

[10] van Zadelhoff F.B., Albaba A., Cohen D., Phillips C., Schaepli B., Dorren L., Schwarz M. 2022. Introducing SlideforMAP: a probabilistic finite slope approach for modelling shallow-landslide probability in forested situations. *Natural Hazards and Earth System Sciences*, 22: 2611–2635. <https://doi.org/10.5194/nhess-22-2611-2022>.

The maps produced require a constant updating process, especially in case of landscape changes caused by human activity, such as construction of infrastructure, mining, etc. ^[11]

Shallow-landslide probability model named SlideforMAP is designed for regional scale (it should be applied on study areas in size of 1 – 1000 km²) to ensure wide applicability.^[12]

About model SlideforMAP

Probabilistic model SlideforMAP generates a 2D raster data of shallow landslide probability by generating a large number of hypothetical landslides on the pre-defined region of interest. Hypothetical landslides generated by SlideforMAP are elliptic in shape and are characterized by 21 probabilistic and deterministic parameters. From those 21 parameters, landslide stability is computed.

Probabilistic parameters characterizing hypothetical landslide are:

- hypothetical landslide location,
- hypothetical landslide surface area,
- hypothetical landslide soil cohesion,
- internal friction angle,
- soil thickness parameters.

Deterministic parameters include:

- several vegetation parameters,
- hydrological soil parameters.

[11] Silva-Protect Project. 2016.Silva-Protect Project in Switzerland <https://www.bafu.admin.ch/bafu/de/home/themen/naturgefahren/fachinformationen/naturgefahrensituation-und-raumnutzung/gefahregrundlagen/silvaproduct-ch.html> (22. 2. 2022)

[12] van Zadelhoff F.B., Albaba A., Cohen D., Phillips C., Schaeffli B., Dorren L., Schwarz M. 2022. Introducing SlideforMAP: a probabilistic finite slope approach for modelling shallow-landslide probability in forested situations. Natural Hazards and Earth System Sciences, 22: 2611–2635. <https://doi.org/10.5194/nhess-22-2611-2022>.

On the picture below, there is a chart that represents computational steps by which model SlideforMAP. The result of SlideforMAP model is the probability of shallow landslide occurrence for each raster cell.

Figure 1: Computational steps of model SlideforMAP.^[13]

The safety factor (as the estimation of hypothetical landslide stability) is calculated.^[14] In this method, it is considered that if the safety factor is greater than 1.0, the hypothetical landslide is assumed to be stable.^[15] The safety factor is the ratio between slope-stabilizing and slope-destabilizing forces.

[13] van Zadelhoff F.B., Albaba A., Cohen D., Phillips C., Schaeffli B., Dorren L., Schwarz M. 2022. Introducing SlideforMAP: a probabilistic finite slope approach for modelling shallow-landslide probability in forested situations. *Natural Hazards and Earth System Sciences*, 22: 2611–2635. <https://doi.org/10.5194/nhess-22-2611-2022>.

[14] van Zadelhoff F.B., Albaba A., Cohen D., Phillips C., Schaeffli B., Dorren L., Schwarz M. 2022. Introducing SlideforMAP: a probabilistic finite slope approach for modelling shallow-landslide probability in forested situations. *Natural Hazards and Earth System Sciences*, 22: 2611–2635. <https://doi.org/10.5194/nhess-22-2611-2022>.

[15] Day R.W. 1997. State of the art: Limit equilibrium and finite-element analysis of slopes. *Journal of Geotechnical and Geoenvironmental Engineering*, 123: 894. [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)1090-0241\(1997\)123:9\(894\)](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)1090-0241(1997)123:9(894)).

Weight, lateral root reinforcement, and basal root reinforcement are properties of vegetation included in model SlideforMAP. For vegetation, the model only includes trees, but not shrubs, grasses, and other vegetation^[16].

SlideforMAP produces data related to the reinforcement of the basal and lateral roots in the investigation area, allowing us to focus on the forest's mitigation effect^[17].

On the table below, there are all the parameters required by SlideforMAP. The first column contains the parameter code, the second the parameter, the third the default value of the parameter, the fourth the unit, the fifth the source, and the sixth the range of the parameter (either global or specific for this research in Switzerland (CH)).

Parameter	Description	Default value	Unit	Source	Extent
m_d	Soil thickness mean	1	m	Estimate	Global
σ_d	Soil thickness standard deviation	0.25	m	Estimate	Global
m_c	Soil cohesion mean	2	kPa	Estimate	Global
σ_c	Soil cohesion standard deviation	0.5	kPa	Estimate	Global
m_ϕ	Angle of internal friction mean	30	°	Estimate	Global
σ_ϕ	Angle of internal standard deviation	4	°	Estimate	Global
ρ_{ls}	Density of the randomly generated landslides	0.1	HL m ⁻²	Estimate	Global
ρ_{soil}	Dry soil density	1500	kg m ⁻³	Estimate	Global
T	Soil transmissivity	0.1	m ² s ⁻¹	Estimate	Global
I	The precipitation event that is tested	10	mm h ⁻¹	Estimate	Global
I_{min}	Precipitation intensity threshold for instability	1.2	mm h ⁻¹	Leonarduzzi et al. (2017)	CH
r_{xy}	Raster resolution of the SlideforMAP run	2	m	Estimate	Global
l_{wr}	Ratio between length and width of the landslides	2	-	Estimate	Global
c	Fitting parameter for the lateral root reinforcement	25068.54	-	Gehring et al. (2019)	CH
α_1	Shape of root distribution in horizontal direction	0.862	-	Gehring et al. (2019)	CH
β_1	Rate of root distribution in horizontal direction	3.225	-	Gehring et al. (2019)	CH
α_2	Shape of root distribution in vertical direction	1.284	-	Gehring et al. (2019)	CH
β_2	Rate of root distribution in vertical direction	3.688	m	Gehring et al. (2019)	CH
$D_{trees, max}$	Maximum distance for influence of the roots	15	m	Estimate	Global
ρ_{tree}	Density of a tree	850	kg m ⁻³	Estimate	CH
ρ_{water}	Density of water	998	kg m ⁻³	Estimate	Global

Table 1: Parameters required by slideforMAP.

[16] van Zadelhoff F.B., Albaba A., Cohen D., Phillips C., Schaeffli B., Dorren L., Schwarz M. 2022. Introducing SlideforMAP: a probabilistic finite slope approach for modelling shallow-landslide probability in forested situations. *Natural Hazards and Earth System Sciences*, 22: 2611–2635. <https://doi.org/10.5194/nhess-22-2611-2022>.

[17] Murgia I., Giadrossich F., Mao Z., Cohen D., Capra G.F., Schwarz M. 2022. Modeling shallow landslides and root reinforcement: A review. *Ecological Engineering*, 2022, 181: 106671. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoleng.2022.106671>.

The model SlideforMAP calculates the probability of shallow landslide occurring on each raster cell. The probability of shallow landslide occurrence is calculated as ratio between number of unstable hypothetical landslides per raster cell and all hypothetical landslides per raster cell.^[18]

Study Areas

SlideforMAP was tested on three study areas in Switzerland. Areas were selected based on the availability of elevation data and detailed records of past events of shallow landslides.

All of them were different in size and were on different locations to test the robustness and general applicability of SlideforMAP. On the figure below, there are locations of all three Swiss study areas. Blue dots represent observed shallow landslide occurrences between the years 1997 and 2012. Case studies were named after nearby villages: Trub, St. Antönien, and Eriz. The green colour represents the area, covered with forest.^[19]

Figure 2: Study areas in Switzerland. ^{[20] [21]}

One case study was made in Italy. The study area was in central Italian Apennines, in the north part of Marche. There, one of the highest peaks with 1525 meters above sea level is Mt. Nerone. The study area, size of approximately 5600 hectares, belongs to the Metauro river catchment.

The effect of vegetation clearly appeared in three simulation scenarios with a 200 year return period. Three scenarios were calculated. One is with no vegetation cover ($200RP_0$), the second one with vegetation cover as it was in 1954 ($200RP_{54}$) and the third one with vegetation cover as it was in 2021 ($200RP_{21}$).

[18] van Zadelhoff F.B., Albaba A., Cohen D., Phillips C., Schaeffli B., Dorren L., Schwarz M. 2022. Introducing SlideforMAP: a probabilistic finite slope approach for modelling shallow-landslide probability in forested situations. *Natural Hazards and Earth System Sciences*, 22: 2611–2635. <https://doi.org/10.5194/nhess-22-2611-2022>.

[19] van Zadelhoff F.B., Albaba A., Cohen D., Phillips C., Schaeffli B., Dorren L., Schwarz M. 2022. Introducing SlideforMAP: a probabilistic finite slope approach for modelling shallow-landslide probability in forested situations. *Natural Hazards and Earth System Sciences*, 22: 2611–2635. <https://doi.org/10.5194/nhess-22-2611-2022>.

[20] Swisstopo: Switzerland forest cover map. <https://www.swisstopo.admin.ch/de/geodata/landscape/tlm3d.html> (29. 9. 2015).

[21] Swisstopo: SwissALTI3D Das hoch auf-gelöste Terrainmodell der Schweiz, LIDAR based Digital Terrain Model, Bundesamt für Landestopografie swisstopo, Wabern, 2018.

The comparison between the 200RP₀, 200RP₅₄ and 200RP₂₁ scenarios highlighted the effect of vegetation cover.

The stable area was smaller in 200RP₀ (29.1 %) compared to 200RP₅₄ (68.2 %). The stable area in 200RP₂₁ (89.7 %) was bigger than 200RP₅₄.^[22]

Figure 3: Study area in Italy^[22]

Input data for SlideforMAP

The model SlideforMAP needs to have some data to compute the probability of landslide occurrences. Those are the digital surface model, digital elevation model, soil thickness mean, soil thickness standard deviation, soil cohesion mean, soil cohesion standard deviation, angle of internal friction mean, angle of internal friction standard deviation, and a landslide inventory.

A landslide inventory should not be present in the study area (if it is, it is probably better). However, a landslide inventory must be representative for the study area, and it must contain at least information on the average landslide soil thickness and landslide surface area.^[23]

[22] Murgia I., Vitali A., Giadrossich F., Tonelli E., Baglioni L., Cohen D., Schwarz M., Urbinati C. 2024. Effects of land cover changes on shallow landslide susceptibility using SlideforMAP software (Mt. Nerone, Italy). *Land*, 2024, 13 (10): 1575 <https://doi.org/10.3390/land13101575>.

[23] van Zadelhoff F.B., Albaba A., Cohen D., Phillips C., Schaeffli B., Dorren L., Schwarz M. 2022. Introducing SlideforMAP: a probabilistic finite slope approach for modelling shallow-landslide probability in forested situations. *Natural Hazards and Earth System Sciences*, 22: 2611–2635. <https://doi.org/10.5194/nhess-22-2611-2022>.

Conclusions

One probable future focus is improving the vegetation module by including different tree species in the parametrization of lateral root reinforcement. The model SlideforMAP analysis could be validated in study areas with a larger inventory of shallow landslides.

A probabilistic model for assessing shallow landslide probability is presented, SlideforMAP. The model is developed to provide a detailed inclusion of root reinforcement influence. The use is illustrated in three mid-elevated case studies from Switzerland, for which past landslides have been monitored.

Parameter analysis has shown that in the studied mountain regions, key parameters in slope stability assessment are soil thickness, cohesion, and precipitation intensity transmissivity ratio.

The focus was on assessing whether the model can study scenarios of vegetation distribution.

Comparison of different scenarios in vegetation type has shown sensitivity to the spatial distribution of vegetation of the model output^[24].

[24] van Zadelhoff F.B., Albaba A., Cohen D., Phillips C., Schaeffli B., Dorren L., Schwarz M. 2022. Introducing SlideforMAP: a probabilistic finite slope approach for modelling shallow-landslide probability in forested situations. *Natural Hazards and Earth System Sciences*, 22: 2611–2635. <https://doi.org/10.5194/nhess-22-2611-2022>.

Further information

[Information from Operational Group's database](#)

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